

Music Students' Psychological Profiles: Unveiling Three Coping Clusters Using Schema Mode Inventory

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Abstract

Background and Aim: Professional musicians face unique psychological demands leading to elevated rates of mental health problems including depression, anxiety, and performance anxiety, as well as stress-related disorders. These difficulties associate with perfectionism, adverse experiences, and maladaptive coping. While schema modes—recurring emotion, cognition, and behavior patterns triggered by early maladaptive schemas—are well-studied in clinical populations, their role in musicians remains unexplored. This study explores schema mode presence in music students to evaluate their utility for understanding psychological vulnerability and coping.

Methods: Forty-six music students from Zurich University of the Arts and Basel Music Academy completed an online survey assessing schema modes (Short Schema Mode Inventory), musician-specific coping (HIL scale), and self-talk via open-ended questions. Analysis included parametric tests comparing normative data from healthy controls and clinical patients, Pearson correlations between schema modes and coping, cluster analysis identifying psychological profiles, and qualitative content analysis.

Results: Music students scored significantly higher on maladaptive schema modes versus non-clinical controls, indicating greater emotional coping difficulties and reduced adaptive resources. Coping capacity correlated negatively with maladaptive modes and positively with healthy adult mode. Scores overlapped with Axis I patients but differed from Axis II patients, suggesting intermediate clinical characteristics. Cluster analysis revealed three distinct profiles: "Balanced Musicians" (resilient cluster with high healthy adult/happy child modes and effective coping), "Vulnerable Musicians" (high-risk cluster with intense emotional child modes and frequent maladaptive parent/coping modes), and "Compensating Musicians" (at-risk cluster with intermediate scores and overcompensating strategies mixing functional and maladaptive modes).

Conclusion: Schema modes appear central to musicians' mental health and coping, highlighting psychological profile heterogeneity among music students. Schema-focused

interventions targeting maladaptive modes may enhance resilience and mental health in this population. This approach offers a promising clinical framework for supporting musicians' wellbeing.

MusicSchemata

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REF	Reference (if provided in link)		
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AN02	NR: Code drawn	495 SN586423
AN02	NR: Code drawn	496 SN636918
AN02	NR: Code drawn	497 SR147764
AN02	NR: Code drawn	498 SR391981
AN02	NR: Code drawn	499 SS199854
AN02	NR: Code drawn	500 ST771293
AN02	NR: Code drawn	501 SU222847
AN02	NR: Code drawn	502 SU489781
AN02	NR: Code drawn	503 SU783535
AN02	NR: Code drawn	504 SU954512
AN02	NR: Code drawn	505 SV125366
AN02	NR: Code drawn	506 SV715144
AN02	NR: Code drawn	507 SV863379
AN02	NR: Code drawn	508 SW141985
AN02	NR: Code drawn	509 SW467542
AN02	NR: Code drawn	510 SW992421
AN02	NR: Code drawn	511 SX284389
AN02	NR: Code drawn	512 SX481751

MusicSchemata

AN02	NR: Code drawn	513 SX614857
AN02	NR: Code drawn	514 SX722537
AN02	NR: Code drawn	515 SX749418
AN02	NR: Code drawn	516 SY223652
AN02	NR: Code drawn	517 TA721153
AN02	NR: Code drawn	518 TA814628
AN02	NR: Code drawn	519 TA931462
AN02	NR: Code drawn	520 TB374762
AN02	NR: Code drawn	521 TB391286
AN02	NR: Code drawn	522 TB837215
AN02	NR: Code drawn	523 TC538431
AN02	NR: Code drawn	524 TD343874
AN02	NR: Code drawn	525 TD444669
AN02	NR: Code drawn	526 TD654951
AN02	NR: Code drawn	527 TE572615
AN02	NR: Code drawn	528 TF621826
AN02	NR: Code drawn	529 TF627428
AN02	NR: Code drawn	530 TG657827
AN02	NR: Code drawn	531 TG845387
AN02	NR: Code drawn	532 TH277264
AN02	NR: Code drawn	533 TK993411
AN02	NR: Code drawn	534 TL361426
AN02	NR: Code drawn	535 TM282586
AN02	NR: Code drawn	536 TN826236
AN02	NR: Code drawn	537 TP751918
AN02	NR: Code drawn	538 TQ249258
AN02	NR: Code drawn	539 TQ272697
AN02	NR: Code drawn	540 TQ894859
AN02	NR: Code drawn	541 TR153524
AN02	NR: Code drawn	542 TS949792
AN02	NR: Code drawn	543 TT112812
AN02	NR: Code drawn	544 TU275799
AN02	NR: Code drawn	545 TU812465
AN02	NR: Code drawn	546 TV213445
AN02	NR: Code drawn	547 TV582468
AN02	NR: Code drawn	548 TV817846
AN02	NR: Code drawn	549 TW184984
AN02	NR: Code drawn	550 TW985573
AN02	NR: Code drawn	551 TX184533
AN02	NR: Code drawn	552 TY656286
AN02	NR: Code drawn	553 TY718916
AN02	NR: Code drawn	554 UA692685
AN02	NR: Code drawn	555 UB141148
AN02	NR: Code drawn	556 UC129882
AN02	NR: Code drawn	557 UC532729
AN02	NR: Code drawn	558 UD143252
AN02	NR: Code drawn	559 UD835827
AN02	NR: Code drawn	560 UD924671
AN02	NR: Code drawn	561 UE371847
AN02	NR: Code drawn	562 UE389662
AN02	NR: Code drawn	563 UE588331
AN02	NR: Code drawn	564 UF974945

MusicSchemata

AN02	NR: Code drawn	565 UG581426
AN02	NR: Code drawn	566 UK743146
AN02	NR: Code drawn	567 UL541856
AN02	NR: Code drawn	568 UL927826
AN02	NR: Code drawn	569 UN772193
AN02	NR: Code drawn	570 UN981892
AN02	NR: Code drawn	571 UQ221682
AN02	NR: Code drawn	572 UR241721
AN02	NR: Code drawn	573 UR936443
AN02	NR: Code drawn	574 US578392
AN02	NR: Code drawn	575 US744684
AN02	NR: Code drawn	576 UT338276
AN02	NR: Code drawn	577 UT831457
AN02	NR: Code drawn	578 UU543378
AN02	NR: Code drawn	579 UU692664
AN02	NR: Code drawn	580 UV214139
AN02	NR: Code drawn	581 UV523359
AN02	NR: Code drawn	582 UV744848
AN02	NR: Code drawn	583 UV936787
AN02	NR: Code drawn	584 UX967695
AN02	NR: Code drawn	585 UY182661
AN02	NR: Code drawn	586 UY261197
AN02	NR: Code drawn	587 UY722928
AN02	NR: Code drawn	588 UZ316619
AN02	NR: Code drawn	589 UZ689814
AN02	NR: Code drawn	590 VA397516
AN02	NR: Code drawn	591 VA412921
AN02	NR: Code drawn	592 VA442245
AN02	NR: Code drawn	593 VA916747
AN02	NR: Code drawn	594 VB552646
AN02	NR: Code drawn	595 VB826154
AN02	NR: Code drawn	596 VC483931
AN02	NR: Code drawn	597 VD818469
AN02	NR: Code drawn	598 VE891925
AN02	NR: Code drawn	599 VF396962
AN02	NR: Code drawn	600 VF556714
AN02	NR: Code drawn	601 VG726344
AN02	NR: Code drawn	602 VH444988
AN02	NR: Code drawn	603 VK273481
AN02	NR: Code drawn	604 VK593436
AN02	NR: Code drawn	605 VK817991
AN02	NR: Code drawn	606 VL222652
AN02	NR: Code drawn	607 VL384168
AN02	NR: Code drawn	608 VM338868
AN02	NR: Code drawn	609 VM775281
AN02	NR: Code drawn	610 VM835714
AN02	NR: Code drawn	611 VN577794
AN02	NR: Code drawn	612 VN851333
AN02	NR: Code drawn	613 VP935893
AN02	NR: Code drawn	614 VQ468864
AN02	NR: Code drawn	615 VS244167
AN02	NR: Code drawn	616 VS325757

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AN02	NR: Code drawn	617 VS714485
AN02	NR: Code drawn	618 VT215245
AN02	NR: Code drawn	619 VV595424
AN02	NR: Code drawn	620 VW947853
AN02	NR: Code drawn	621 VX483817
AN02	NR: Code drawn	622 VY595752
AN02	NR: Code drawn	623 VY693565
AN02	NR: Code drawn	624 VZ499885
AN02	NR: Code drawn	625 VZ635856
AN02	NR: Code drawn	626 VZ814496
AN02	NR: Code drawn	627 WA623373
AN02	NR: Code drawn	628 WB384372
AN02	NR: Code drawn	629 WD216147
AN02	NR: Code drawn	630 WE643261
AN02	NR: Code drawn	631 WG846664
AN02	NR: Code drawn	632 WH451744
AN02	NR: Code drawn	633 WH814985
AN02	NR: Code drawn	634 WK373818
AN02	NR: Code drawn	635 WK958861
AN02	NR: Code drawn	636 WL188132
AN02	NR: Code drawn	637 WL195597
AN02	NR: Code drawn	638 WL433443
AN02	NR: Code drawn	639 WQ227326
AN02	NR: Code drawn	640 WR192981
AN02	NR: Code drawn	641 WS873742
AN02	NR: Code drawn	642 WT721724
AN02	NR: Code drawn	643 WT837689
AN02	NR: Code drawn	644 WT946958
AN02	NR: Code drawn	645 WU283318
AN02	NR: Code drawn	646 WU492318
AN02	NR: Code drawn	647 WU748348
AN02	NR: Code drawn	648 WV315925
AN02	NR: Code drawn	649 WV613647
AN02	NR: Code drawn	650 WV974261
AN02	NR: Code drawn	651 WW437263
AN02	NR: Code drawn	652 WW871371
AN02	NR: Code drawn	653 WX287558
AN02	NR: Code drawn	654 WX326445
AN02	NR: Code drawn	655 WY868638
AN02	NR: Code drawn	656 XA445475
AN02	NR: Code drawn	657 XA787699
AN02	NR: Code drawn	658 XA829243
AN02	NR: Code drawn	659 XB317562
AN02	NR: Code drawn	660 XB735525
AN02	NR: Code drawn	661 XB985739
AN02	NR: Code drawn	662 XD454366
AN02	NR: Code drawn	663 XD465798
AN02	NR: Code drawn	664 XD995532
AN02	NR: Code drawn	665 XE729916
AN02	NR: Code drawn	666 XF214729
AN02	NR: Code drawn	667 XF327774
AN02	NR: Code drawn	668 XH789153

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AN02	NR: Code drawn	669 XL756718
AN02	NR: Code drawn	670 XN643561
AN02	NR: Code drawn	671 XN868989
AN02	NR: Code drawn	672 XP983519
AN02	NR: Code drawn	673 XR283772
AN02	NR: Code drawn	674 XS579213
AN02	NR: Code drawn	675 XT155923
AN02	NR: Code drawn	676 XU246264
AN02	NR: Code drawn	677 XU322831
AN02	NR: Code drawn	678 XU877313
AN02	NR: Code drawn	679 XV287499
AN02	NR: Code drawn	680 XV845156
AN02	NR: Code drawn	681 XW523697
AN02	NR: Code drawn	682 XZ296935
AN02	NR: Code drawn	683 XZ521963
AN02	NR: Code drawn	684 YA481937
AN02	NR: Code drawn	685 YA727755
AN02	NR: Code drawn	686 YA746368
AN02	NR: Code drawn	687 YA864494
AN02	NR: Code drawn	688 YC923351
AN02	NR: Code drawn	689 YC934614
AN02	NR: Code drawn	690 YD261484
AN02	NR: Code drawn	691 YD312114
AN02	NR: Code drawn	692 YD827944
AN02	NR: Code drawn	693 YF487642
AN02	NR: Code drawn	694 YG633179
AN02	NR: Code drawn	695 YH236114
AN02	NR: Code drawn	696 YH421443
AN02	NR: Code drawn	697 YK143883
AN02	NR: Code drawn	698 YM182726
AN02	NR: Code drawn	699 YN769952
AN02	NR: Code drawn	700 YP317584
AN02	NR: Code drawn	701 YP523972
AN02	NR: Code drawn	702 YP818859
AN02	NR: Code drawn	703 YP862496
AN02	NR: Code drawn	704 YQ726336
AN02	NR: Code drawn	705 YQ813754
AN02	NR: Code drawn	706 YT564232
AN02	NR: Code drawn	707 YT669994
AN02	NR: Code drawn	708 YT839599
AN02	NR: Code drawn	709 YV718275
AN02	NR: Code drawn	710 YW393431
AN02	NR: Code drawn	711 YW417919
AN02	NR: Code drawn	712 YX651235
AN02	NR: Code drawn	713 YX832439
AN02	NR: Code drawn	714 YX878115
AN02	NR: Code drawn	715 YY218637
AN02	NR: Code drawn	716 YY618726
AN02	NR: Code drawn	717 YZ361232
AN02	NR: Code drawn	718 YZ426738
AN02	NR: Code drawn	719 ZA161285
AN02	NR: Code drawn	720 ZB441721

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AN02	NR: Code drawn	721 ZC434142
AN02	NR: Code drawn	722 ZF328452
AN02	NR: Code drawn	723 ZF523186
AN02	NR: Code drawn	724 ZF523794
AN02	NR: Code drawn	725 ZG165887
AN02	NR: Code drawn	726 ZG634161
AN02	NR: Code drawn	727 ZL297691
AN02	NR: Code drawn	728 ZL331849
AN02	NR: Code drawn	729 ZL535342
AN02	NR: Code drawn	730 ZL536652
AN02	NR: Code drawn	731 ZL641972
AN02	NR: Code drawn	732 ZM719239
AN02	NR: Code drawn	733 ZN552121
AN02	NR: Code drawn	734 ZQ278167
AN02	NR: Code drawn	735 ZS333299
AN02	NR: Code drawn	736 ZT167281
AN02	NR: Code drawn	737 ZT373687
AN02	NR: Code drawn	738 ZT592996
AN02	NR: Code drawn	739 ZT693739
AN02	NR: Code drawn	740 ZU299219
AN02	NR: Code drawn	741 ZU531788
AN02	NR: Code drawn	742 ZW651299
AN02	NR: Code drawn	743 ZW788821
AN02	NR: Code drawn	744 ZW827662
AN02	NR: Code drawn	745 ZW911453
AN02	NR: Code drawn	746 ZX621952
AN02	NR: Code drawn	747 ZX827895
AN02	NR: Code drawn	748 ZY312759
AN02	NR: Code drawn	749 ZY743517
AN02	NR: Code drawn	750 ZZ531412
AN03	status	1 I am still a music student.
AN03	status	2 I am a music professional/not studying a
AN03	status	3 I am interested in future workshops and
AN03	status	-1 other
AN03	status	-9 Not answered
EP01_01	HIL Skala: I am satisfied with the succe:	1 Strongly agree
EP01_01	HIL Skala: I am satisfied with the succe:	2 Agree
EP01_01	HIL Skala: I am satisfied with the succe:	3 Somewhat agree
EP01_01	HIL Skala: I am satisfied with the succe:	4 Disagree somewhat
EP01_01	HIL Skala: I am satisfied with the succe:	5 Disagree
EP01_01	HIL Skala: I am satisfied with the succe:	6 Strongly Disagree
EP01_01	HIL Skala: I am satisfied with the succe:	-9 Not answered
EP01_02	HIL Skala: My posture feels good while	1 Strongly agree
EP01_02	HIL Skala: My posture feels good while	2 Agree
EP01_02	HIL Skala: My posture feels good while	3 Somewhat agree
EP01_02	HIL Skala: My posture feels good while	4 Disagree somewhat
EP01_02	HIL Skala: My posture feels good while	5 Disagree
EP01_02	HIL Skala: My posture feels good while	6 Strongly Disagree
EP01_02	HIL Skala: My posture feels good while	-9 Not answered
EP01_03	HIL Skala: My breathing feels good whil	1 Strongly agree
EP01_03	HIL Skala: My breathing feels good whil	2 Agree
EP01_03	HIL Skala: My breathing feels good whil	3 Somewhat agree

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EP01_03	HIL Skala: My breathing feels good whil	4 Disagree somewhat
EP01_03	HIL Skala: My breathing feels good whil	5 Disagree
EP01_03	HIL Skala: My breathing feels good whil	6 Strongly Disagree
EP01_03	HIL Skala: My breathing feels good whil	-9 Not answered
EP01_04	HIL Skala: I feel confident in stage situa	1 Strongly agree
EP01_04	HIL Skala: I feel confident in stage situa	2 Agree
EP01_04	HIL Skala: I feel confident in stage situa	3 Somewhat agree
EP01_04	HIL Skala: I feel confident in stage situa	4 Disagree somewhat
EP01_04	HIL Skala: I feel confident in stage situa	5 Disagree
EP01_04	HIL Skala: I feel confident in stage situa	6 Strongly Disagree
EP01_04	HIL Skala: I feel confident in stage situa	-9 Not answered
EP01_05	HIL Skala: My playing movements feel c	1 Strongly agree
EP01_05	HIL Skala: My playing movements feel c	2 Agree
EP01_05	HIL Skala: My playing movements feel c	3 Somewhat agree
EP01_05	HIL Skala: My playing movements feel c	4 Disagree somewhat
EP01_05	HIL Skala: My playing movements feel c	5 Disagree
EP01_05	HIL Skala: My playing movements feel c	6 Strongly Disagree
EP01_05	HIL Skala: My playing movements feel c	-9 Not answered
EP01_06	HIL Skala: I have complaints related to i	1 Strongly agree
EP01_06	HIL Skala: I have complaints related to i	2 Agree
EP01_06	HIL Skala: I have complaints related to i	3 Somewhat agree
EP01_06	HIL Skala: I have complaints related to i	4 Disagree somewhat
EP01_06	HIL Skala: I have complaints related to i	5 Disagree
EP01_06	HIL Skala: I have complaints related to i	6 Strongly Disagree
EP01_06	HIL Skala: I have complaints related to i	-9 Not answered
EP01_07	HIL Skala: I feel capable in my studies /	1 Strongly agree
EP01_07	HIL Skala: I feel capable in my studies /	2 Agree
EP01_07	HIL Skala: I feel capable in my studies /	3 Somewhat agree
EP01_07	HIL Skala: I feel capable in my studies /	4 Disagree somewhat
EP01_07	HIL Skala: I feel capable in my studies /	5 Disagree
EP01_07	HIL Skala: I feel capable in my studies /	6 Strongly Disagree
EP01_07	HIL Skala: I feel capable in my studies /	-9 Not answered
EP02_03	HIL Texteingabe: Optional: If you have complaints related to making music, what are they?	
EP02_04	HIL Texteingabe: Optional: If you have/have had problems with a teacher or orchestra or chamberm	
EP02_05	HIL Texteingabe: Optional: What are typical thoughts (positive and negative) you have in musical sit	
MU01	Main Instrument	-2 other text response
MU01	Main Instrument	-9 Not answered
MU01s	Main Instrument (free text)	
MU02	School	1 Zürcher Hochschule der Künste
MU02	School	2 Musikhochschule Basel
MU02	School	3 Zurich University of the Arts
MU02	School	4 Konservatorium Winterthur
MU02	School	5 Musikhochschule Bern
MU02	School	-2 other text response
MU02	School	-9 Not answered
MU02s	School (free text)	
MU06_01	Study program: [01]	
SC01_02	Set1: I demand respect by not letting otl	1 Never or almost never
SC01_02	Set1: I demand respect by not letting otl	2 Rarely
SC01_02	Set1: I demand respect by not letting otl	3 Occasionally
SC01_02	Set1: I demand respect by not letting otl	4 Frequently
SC01_02	Set1: I demand respect by not letting otl	5 Most of the time

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SC01_02	Set1: I demand respect by not letting otl	6 Always
SC01_02	Set1: I demand respect by not letting otl	-9 Not answered
SC01_03	Set1: I feel loved and accepted.	1 Never or almost never
SC01_03	Set1: I feel loved and accepted.	2 Rarely
SC01_03	Set1: I feel loved and accepted.	3 Occasionally
SC01_03	Set1: I feel loved and accepted.	4 Frequently
SC01_03	Set1: I feel loved and accepted.	5 Most of the time
SC01_03	Set1: I feel loved and accepted.	6 Always
SC01_03	Set1: I feel loved and accepted.	-9 Not answered
SC01_04	Set1: I deny myself pleasure because I	1 Never or almost never
SC01_04	Set1: I deny myself pleasure because I	2 Rarely
SC01_04	Set1: I deny myself pleasure because I	3 Occasionally
SC01_04	Set1: I deny myself pleasure because I	4 Frequently
SC01_04	Set1: I deny myself pleasure because I	5 Most of the time
SC01_04	Set1: I deny myself pleasure because I	6 Always
SC01_04	Set1: I deny myself pleasure because I	-9 Not answered
SC01_05	Set1: I feel fundamentally inadequate, fl	1 Never or almost never
SC01_05	Set1: I feel fundamentally inadequate, fl	2 Rarely
SC01_05	Set1: I feel fundamentally inadequate, fl	3 Occasionally
SC01_05	Set1: I feel fundamentally inadequate, fl	4 Frequently
SC01_05	Set1: I feel fundamentally inadequate, fl	5 Most of the time
SC01_05	Set1: I feel fundamentally inadequate, fl	6 Always
SC01_05	Set1: I feel fundamentally inadequate, fl	-9 Not answered
SC01_06	Set1: I have impulses to punish myself t	1 Never or almost never
SC01_06	Set1: I have impulses to punish myself t	2 Rarely
SC01_06	Set1: I have impulses to punish myself t	3 Occasionally
SC01_06	Set1: I have impulses to punish myself t	4 Frequently
SC01_06	Set1: I have impulses to punish myself t	5 Most of the time
SC01_06	Set1: I have impulses to punish myself t	6 Always
SC01_06	Set1: I have impulses to punish myself t	-9 Not answered
SC01_07	Set1: I feel lost.	1 Never or almost never
SC01_07	Set1: I feel lost.	2 Rarely
SC01_07	Set1: I feel lost.	3 Occasionally
SC01_07	Set1: I feel lost.	4 Frequently
SC01_07	Set1: I feel lost.	5 Most of the time
SC01_07	Set1: I feel lost.	6 Always
SC01_07	Set1: I feel lost.	-9 Not answered
SC01_08	Set1: I'm hard on myself.	1 Never or almost never
SC01_08	Set1: I'm hard on myself.	2 Rarely
SC01_08	Set1: I'm hard on myself.	3 Occasionally
SC01_08	Set1: I'm hard on myself.	4 Frequently
SC01_08	Set1: I'm hard on myself.	5 Most of the time
SC01_08	Set1: I'm hard on myself.	6 Always
SC01_08	Set1: I'm hard on myself.	-9 Not answered
SC01_09	Set1: I try very hard to please other peo	1 Never or almost never
SC01_09	Set1: I try very hard to please other peo	2 Rarely
SC01_09	Set1: I try very hard to please other peo	3 Occasionally
SC01_09	Set1: I try very hard to please other peo	4 Frequently
SC01_09	Set1: I try very hard to please other peo	5 Most of the time
SC01_09	Set1: I try very hard to please other peo	6 Always
SC01_09	Set1: I try very hard to please other peo	-9 Not answered
SC01_10	Set1: I can't forgive myself.	1 Never or almost never

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SC01_10	Set1: I can't forgive myself.	2 Rarely
SC01_10	Set1: I can't forgive myself.	3 Occasionally
SC01_10	Set1: I can't forgive myself.	4 Frequently
SC01_10	Set1: I can't forgive myself.	5 Most of the time
SC01_10	Set1: I can't forgive myself.	6 Always
SC01_10	Set1: I can't forgive myself.	-9 Not answered
SC01_11	Set1: I do things to make myself the cer	1 Never or almost never
SC01_11	Set1: I do things to make myself the cer	2 Rarely
SC01_11	Set1: I do things to make myself the cer	3 Occasionally
SC01_11	Set1: I do things to make myself the cer	4 Frequently
SC01_11	Set1: I do things to make myself the cer	5 Most of the time
SC01_11	Set1: I do things to make myself the cer	6 Always
SC01_11	Set1: I do things to make myself the cer	-9 Not answered
SC01_12	Set1: I get irritated when people don't d	1 Never or almost never
SC01_12	Set1: I get irritated when people don't d	2 Rarely
SC01_12	Set1: I get irritated when people don't d	3 Occasionally
SC01_12	Set1: I get irritated when people don't d	4 Frequently
SC01_12	Set1: I get irritated when people don't d	5 Most of the time
SC01_12	Set1: I get irritated when people don't d	6 Always
SC01_12	Set1: I get irritated when people don't d	-9 Not answered
SC01_13	Set1: I have trouble controlling my impu	1 Never or almost never
SC01_13	Set1: I have trouble controlling my impu	2 Rarely
SC01_13	Set1: I have trouble controlling my impu	3 Occasionally
SC01_13	Set1: I have trouble controlling my impu	4 Frequently
SC01_13	Set1: I have trouble controlling my impu	5 Most of the time
SC01_13	Set1: I have trouble controlling my impu	6 Always
SC01_13	Set1: I have trouble controlling my impu	-9 Not answered
SC01_14	Set1: If I can't reach a goal, I become e	1 Never or almost never
SC01_14	Set1: If I can't reach a goal, I become e	2 Rarely
SC01_14	Set1: If I can't reach a goal, I become e	3 Occasionally
SC01_14	Set1: If I can't reach a goal, I become e	4 Frequently
SC01_14	Set1: If I can't reach a goal, I become e	5 Most of the time
SC01_14	Set1: If I can't reach a goal, I become e	6 Always
SC01_14	Set1: If I can't reach a goal, I become e	-9 Not answered
SC01_15	Set1: I have rage outbursts.	1 Never or almost never
SC01_15	Set1: I have rage outbursts.	2 Rarely
SC01_15	Set1: I have rage outbursts.	3 Occasionally
SC01_15	Set1: I have rage outbursts.	4 Frequently
SC01_15	Set1: I have rage outbursts.	5 Most of the time
SC01_15	Set1: I have rage outbursts.	6 Always
SC01_15	Set1: I have rage outbursts.	-9 Not answered
SC01_16	Set1: I act impulsively or express emotik	1 Never or almost never
SC01_16	Set1: I act impulsively or express emotik	2 Rarely
SC01_16	Set1: I act impulsively or express emotik	3 Occasionally
SC01_16	Set1: I act impulsively or express emotik	4 Frequently
SC01_16	Set1: I act impulsively or express emotik	5 Most of the time
SC01_16	Set1: I act impulsively or express emotik	6 Always
SC01_16	Set1: I act impulsively or express emotik	-9 Not answered
SC01_17	Set1: It's my fault when something bad l	1 Never or almost never
SC01_17	Set1: It's my fault when something bad l	2 Rarely
SC01_17	Set1: It's my fault when something bad l	3 Occasionally
SC01_17	Set1: It's my fault when something bad l	4 Frequently

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SC01_17	Set1: It's my fault when something bad	5 Most of the time
SC01_17	Set1: It's my fault when something bad	6 Always
SC01_17	Set1: It's my fault when something bad	-9 Not answered
SC01_18	Set1: I feel content and at ease.	1 Never or almost never
SC01_18	Set1: I feel content and at ease.	2 Rarely
SC01_18	Set1: I feel content and at ease.	3 Occasionally
SC01_18	Set1: I feel content and at ease.	4 Frequently
SC01_18	Set1: I feel content and at ease.	5 Most of the time
SC01_18	Set1: I feel content and at ease.	6 Always
SC01_18	Set1: I feel content and at ease.	-9 Not answered
SC01_19	Set1: I change myself depending on the	1 Never or almost never
SC01_19	Set1: I change myself depending on the	2 Rarely
SC01_19	Set1: I change myself depending on the	3 Occasionally
SC01_19	Set1: I change myself depending on the	4 Frequently
SC01_19	Set1: I change myself depending on the	5 Most of the time
SC01_19	Set1: I change myself depending on the	6 Always
SC01_19	Set1: I change myself depending on the	-9 Not answered
SC01_20	Set1: I feel connected to other people.	1 Never or almost never
SC01_20	Set1: I feel connected to other people.	2 Rarely
SC01_20	Set1: I feel connected to other people.	3 Occasionally
SC01_20	Set1: I feel connected to other people.	4 Frequently
SC01_20	Set1: I feel connected to other people.	5 Most of the time
SC01_20	Set1: I feel connected to other people.	6 Always
SC01_20	Set1: I feel connected to other people.	-9 Not answered
SC01_21	Set1: When there are problems, I try ha	1 Never or almost never
SC01_21	Set1: When there are problems, I try ha	2 Rarely
SC01_21	Set1: When there are problems, I try ha	3 Occasionally
SC01_21	Set1: When there are problems, I try ha	4 Frequently
SC01_21	Set1: When there are problems, I try ha	5 Most of the time
SC01_21	Set1: When there are problems, I try ha	6 Always
SC01_21	Set1: When there are problems, I try ha	-9 Not answered
SC01_22	Set1: I don't discipline myself to comple	1 Never or almost never
SC01_22	Set1: I don't discipline myself to comple	2 Rarely
SC01_22	Set1: I don't discipline myself to comple	3 Occasionally
SC01_22	Set1: I don't discipline myself to comple	4 Frequently
SC01_22	Set1: I don't discipline myself to comple	5 Most of the time
SC01_22	Set1: I don't discipline myself to comple	6 Always
SC01_22	Set1: I don't discipline myself to comple	-9 Not answered
SC01_23	Set1: If I don't fight, I will be abused or i	1 Never or almost never
SC01_23	Set1: If I don't fight, I will be abused or i	2 Rarely
SC01_23	Set1: If I don't fight, I will be abused or i	3 Occasionally
SC01_23	Set1: If I don't fight, I will be abused or i	4 Frequently
SC01_23	Set1: If I don't fight, I will be abused or i	5 Most of the time
SC01_23	Set1: If I don't fight, I will be abused or i	6 Always
SC01_23	Set1: If I don't fight, I will be abused or i	-9 Not answered
SC01_24	Set1: If you let other people mock or bul	1 Never or almost never
SC01_24	Set1: If you let other people mock or bul	2 Rarely
SC01_24	Set1: If you let other people mock or bul	3 Occasionally
SC01_24	Set1: If you let other people mock or bul	4 Frequently
SC01_24	Set1: If you let other people mock or bul	5 Most of the time
SC01_24	Set1: If you let other people mock or bul	6 Always
SC01_24	Set1: If you let other people mock or bul	-9 Not answered

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SC01_25	Set1: I physically attack people when I'n	1 Never or almost never
SC01_25	Set1: I physically attack people when I'n	2 Rarely
SC01_25	Set1: I physically attack people when I'n	3 Occasionally
SC01_25	Set1: I physically attack people when I'n	4 Frequently
SC01_25	Set1: I physically attack people when I'n	5 Most of the time
SC01_25	Set1: I physically attack people when I'n	6 Always
SC01_25	Set1: I physically attack people when I'n	-9 Not answered
SC01_26	Set1: Once I start to feel angry, I often c	1 Never or almost never
SC01_26	Set1: Once I start to feel angry, I often c	2 Rarely
SC01_26	Set1: Once I start to feel angry, I often c	3 Occasionally
SC01_26	Set1: Once I start to feel angry, I often c	4 Frequently
SC01_26	Set1: Once I start to feel angry, I often c	5 Most of the time
SC01_26	Set1: Once I start to feel angry, I often c	6 Always
SC01_26	Set1: Once I start to feel angry, I often c	-9 Not answered
SC01_27	Set1: It's important for me to be Numbe	1 Never or almost never
SC01_27	Set1: It's important for me to be Numbe	2 Rarely
SC01_27	Set1: It's important for me to be Numbe	3 Occasionally
SC01_27	Set1: It's important for me to be Numbe	4 Frequently
SC01_27	Set1: It's important for me to be Numbe	5 Most of the time
SC01_27	Set1: It's important for me to be Numbe	6 Always
SC01_27	Set1: It's important for me to be Numbe	-9 Not answered
SC01_28	Set1: I feel indifferent about most things	1 Never or almost never
SC01_28	Set1: I feel indifferent about most things	2 Rarely
SC01_28	Set1: I feel indifferent about most things	3 Occasionally
SC01_28	Set1: I feel indifferent about most things	4 Frequently
SC01_28	Set1: I feel indifferent about most things	5 Most of the time
SC01_28	Set1: I feel indifferent about most things	6 Always
SC01_28	Set1: I feel indifferent about most things	-9 Not answered
SC01_29	Set1: I can solve problems rationally wit	1 Never or almost never
SC01_29	Set1: I can solve problems rationally wit	2 Rarely
SC01_29	Set1: I can solve problems rationally wit	3 Occasionally
SC01_29	Set1: I can solve problems rationally wit	4 Frequently
SC01_29	Set1: I can solve problems rationally wit	5 Most of the time
SC01_29	Set1: I can solve problems rationally wit	6 Always
SC01_29	Set1: I can solve problems rationally wit	-9 Not answered
SC01_30	Set1: I won't settle for second best.	1 Never or almost never
SC01_30	Set1: I won't settle for second best.	2 Rarely
SC01_30	Set1: I won't settle for second best.	3 Occasionally
SC01_30	Set1: I won't settle for second best.	4 Frequently
SC01_30	Set1: I won't settle for second best.	5 Most of the time
SC01_30	Set1: I won't settle for second best.	6 Always
SC01_30	Set1: I won't settle for second best.	-9 Not answered
SC01_31	Set1: Attacking is the best defense.	1 Never or almost never
SC01_31	Set1: Attacking is the best defense.	2 Rarely
SC01_31	Set1: Attacking is the best defense.	3 Occasionally
SC01_31	Set1: Attacking is the best defense.	4 Frequently
SC01_31	Set1: Attacking is the best defense.	5 Most of the time
SC01_31	Set1: Attacking is the best defense.	6 Always
SC01_31	Set1: Attacking is the best defense.	-9 Not answered
SC02_01	Set2: I feel cold and heartless toward ot	1 Never or almost never
SC02_01	Set2: I feel cold and heartless toward ot	2 Rarely
SC02_01	Set2: I feel cold and heartless toward ot	3 Occasionally

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SC02_01	Set2: I feel cold and heartless toward ot	4 Frequently
SC02_01	Set2: I feel cold and heartless toward ot	5 Most of the time
SC02_01	Set2: I feel cold and heartless toward ot	6 Always
SC02_01	Set2: I feel cold and heartless toward ot	-9 Not answered
SC02_02	Set2: I feel detached (no contact with m	1 Never or almost never
SC02_02	Set2: I feel detached (no contact with m	2 Rarely
SC02_02	Set2: I feel detached (no contact with m	3 Occasionally
SC02_02	Set2: I feel detached (no contact with m	4 Frequently
SC02_02	Set2: I feel detached (no contact with m	5 Most of the time
SC02_02	Set2: I feel detached (no contact with m	6 Always
SC02_02	Set2: I feel detached (no contact with m	-9 Not answered
SC02_03	Set2: I blindly follow my emotions.	1 Never or almost never
SC02_03	Set2: I blindly follow my emotions.	2 Rarely
SC02_03	Set2: I blindly follow my emotions.	3 Occasionally
SC02_03	Set2: I blindly follow my emotions.	4 Frequently
SC02_03	Set2: I blindly follow my emotions.	5 Most of the time
SC02_03	Set2: I blindly follow my emotions.	6 Always
SC02_03	Set2: I blindly follow my emotions.	-9 Not answered
SC02_04	Set2: I feel desperate.	1 Never or almost never
SC02_04	Set2: I feel desperate.	2 Rarely
SC02_04	Set2: I feel desperate.	3 Occasionally
SC02_04	Set2: I feel desperate.	4 Frequently
SC02_04	Set2: I feel desperate.	5 Most of the time
SC02_04	Set2: I feel desperate.	6 Always
SC02_04	Set2: I feel desperate.	-9 Not answered
SC02_05	Set2: I allow other people to criticize me	1 Never or almost never
SC02_05	Set2: I allow other people to criticize me	2 Rarely
SC02_05	Set2: I allow other people to criticize me	3 Occasionally
SC02_05	Set2: I allow other people to criticize me	4 Frequently
SC02_05	Set2: I allow other people to criticize me	5 Most of the time
SC02_05	Set2: I allow other people to criticize me	6 Always
SC02_05	Set2: I allow other people to criticize me	-9 Not answered
SC02_06	Set2: In relationships, I let the other per:	1 Never or almost never
SC02_06	Set2: In relationships, I let the other per:	2 Rarely
SC02_06	Set2: In relationships, I let the other per:	3 Occasionally
SC02_06	Set2: In relationships, I let the other per:	4 Frequently
SC02_06	Set2: In relationships, I let the other per:	5 Most of the time
SC02_06	Set2: In relationships, I let the other per:	6 Always
SC02_06	Set2: In relationships, I let the other per:	-9 Not answered
SC02_07	Set2: I feel distant from other people.	1 Never or almost never
SC02_07	Set2: I feel distant from other people.	2 Rarely
SC02_07	Set2: I feel distant from other people.	3 Occasionally
SC02_07	Set2: I feel distant from other people.	4 Frequently
SC02_07	Set2: I feel distant from other people.	5 Most of the time
SC02_07	Set2: I feel distant from other people.	6 Always
SC02_07	Set2: I feel distant from other people.	-9 Not answered
SC02_08	Set2: I don't think about what I say, and	1 Never or almost never
SC02_08	Set2: I don't think about what I say, and	2 Rarely
SC02_08	Set2: I don't think about what I say, and	3 Occasionally
SC02_08	Set2: I don't think about what I say, and	4 Frequently
SC02_08	Set2: I don't think about what I say, and	5 Most of the time
SC02_08	Set2: I don't think about what I say, and	6 Always

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SC02_08	Set2: I don't think about what I say, and	-9 Not answered
SC02_09	Set2: I work or play sports intensively sc	1 Never or almost never
SC02_09	Set2: I work or play sports intensively sc	2 Rarely
SC02_09	Set2: I work or play sports intensively sc	3 Occasionally
SC02_09	Set2: I work or play sports intensively sc	4 Frequently
SC02_09	Set2: I work or play sports intensively sc	5 Most of the time
SC02_09	Set2: I work or play sports intensively sc	6 Always
SC02_09	Set2: I work or play sports intensively sc	-9 Not answered
SC02_10	Set2: I'm angry that people are trying to	1 Never or almost never
SC02_10	Set2: I'm angry that people are trying to	2 Rarely
SC02_10	Set2: I'm angry that people are trying to	3 Occasionally
SC02_10	Set2: I'm angry that people are trying to	4 Frequently
SC02_10	Set2: I'm angry that people are trying to	5 Most of the time
SC02_10	Set2: I'm angry that people are trying to	6 Always
SC02_10	Set2: I'm angry that people are trying to	-9 Not answered
SC02_11	Set2: I feel nothing.	1 Never or almost never
SC02_11	Set2: I feel nothing.	2 Rarely
SC02_11	Set2: I feel nothing.	3 Occasionally
SC02_11	Set2: I feel nothing.	4 Frequently
SC02_11	Set2: I feel nothing.	5 Most of the time
SC02_11	Set2: I feel nothing.	6 Always
SC02_11	Set2: I feel nothing.	-9 Not answered
SC02_12	Set2: I do what I want to do, regardless	1 Never or almost never
SC02_12	Set2: I do what I want to do, regardless	2 Rarely
SC02_12	Set2: I do what I want to do, regardless	3 Occasionally
SC02_12	Set2: I do what I want to do, regardless	4 Frequently
SC02_12	Set2: I do what I want to do, regardless	5 Most of the time
SC02_12	Set2: I do what I want to do, regardless	6 Always
SC02_12	Set2: I do what I want to do, regardless	-9 Not answered
SC02_13	Set2: I don't let myself relax or have fun	1 Never or almost never
SC02_13	Set2: I don't let myself relax or have fun	2 Rarely
SC02_13	Set2: I don't let myself relax or have fun	3 Occasionally
SC02_13	Set2: I don't let myself relax or have fun	4 Frequently
SC02_13	Set2: I don't let myself relax or have fun	5 Most of the time
SC02_13	Set2: I don't let myself relax or have fun	6 Always
SC02_13	Set2: I don't let myself relax or have fun	-9 Not answered
SC02_14	Set2: I throw things around when I'm an	1 Never or almost never
SC02_14	Set2: I throw things around when I'm an	2 Rarely
SC02_14	Set2: I throw things around when I'm an	3 Occasionally
SC02_14	Set2: I throw things around when I'm an	4 Frequently
SC02_14	Set2: I throw things around when I'm an	5 Most of the time
SC02_14	Set2: I throw things around when I'm an	6 Always
SC02_14	Set2: I throw things around when I'm an	-9 Not answered
SC02_15	Set2: I feel enraged toward other people	1 Never or almost never
SC02_15	Set2: I feel enraged toward other people	2 Rarely
SC02_15	Set2: I feel enraged toward other people	3 Occasionally
SC02_15	Set2: I feel enraged toward other people	4 Frequently
SC02_15	Set2: I feel enraged toward other people	5 Most of the time
SC02_15	Set2: I feel enraged toward other people	6 Always
SC02_15	Set2: I feel enraged toward other people	-9 Not answered
SC02_16	Set2: I feel that I fit in with other people.	1 Never or almost never
SC02_16	Set2: I feel that I fit in with other people.	2 Rarely

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SC02_16	Set2: I feel that I fit in with other people.	3 Occasionally
SC02_16	Set2: I feel that I fit in with other people.	4 Frequently
SC02_16	Set2: I feel that I fit in with other people.	5 Most of the time
SC02_16	Set2: I feel that I fit in with other people.	6 Always
SC02_16	Set2: I feel that I fit in with other people.	-9 Not answered
SC02_17	Set2: I have a lot of anger built up inside	1 Never or almost never
SC02_17	Set2: I have a lot of anger built up inside	2 Rarely
SC02_17	Set2: I have a lot of anger built up inside	3 Occasionally
SC02_17	Set2: I have a lot of anger built up inside	4 Frequently
SC02_17	Set2: I have a lot of anger built up inside	5 Most of the time
SC02_17	Set2: I have a lot of anger built up inside	6 Always
SC02_17	Set2: I have a lot of anger built up inside	-9 Not answered
SC02_18	Set2: I feel lonely.	1 Never or almost never
SC02_18	Set2: I feel lonely.	2 Rarely
SC02_18	Set2: I feel lonely.	3 Occasionally
SC02_18	Set2: I feel lonely.	4 Frequently
SC02_18	Set2: I feel lonely.	5 Most of the time
SC02_18	Set2: I feel lonely.	6 Always
SC02_18	Set2: I feel lonely.	-9 Not answered
SC02_19	Set2: I like doing something exciting or s	1 Never or almost never
SC02_19	Set2: I like doing something exciting or s	2 Rarely
SC02_19	Set2: I like doing something exciting or s	3 Occasionally
SC02_19	Set2: I like doing something exciting or s	4 Frequently
SC02_19	Set2: I like doing something exciting or s	5 Most of the time
SC02_19	Set2: I like doing something exciting or s	6 Always
SC02_19	Set2: I like doing something exciting or s	-9 Not answered
SC02_20	Set2: Equality doesn't exist, so it's bette	1 Never or almost never
SC02_20	Set2: Equality doesn't exist, so it's bette	2 Rarely
SC02_20	Set2: Equality doesn't exist, so it's bette	3 Occasionally
SC02_20	Set2: Equality doesn't exist, so it's bette	4 Frequently
SC02_20	Set2: Equality doesn't exist, so it's bette	5 Most of the time
SC02_20	Set2: Equality doesn't exist, so it's bette	6 Always
SC02_20	Set2: Equality doesn't exist, so it's bette	-9 Not answered
SC02_21	Set2: When I'm angry, I often lose contr	1 Never or almost never
SC02_21	Set2: When I'm angry, I often lose contr	2 Rarely
SC02_21	Set2: When I'm angry, I often lose contr	3 Occasionally
SC02_21	Set2: When I'm angry, I often lose contr	4 Frequently
SC02_21	Set2: When I'm angry, I often lose contr	5 Most of the time
SC02_21	Set2: When I'm angry, I often lose contr	6 Always
SC02_21	Set2: When I'm angry, I often lose contr	-9 Not answered
SC02_22	Set2: I let other people get their own wa	1 Never or almost never
SC02_22	Set2: I let other people get their own wa	2 Rarely
SC02_22	Set2: I let other people get their own wa	3 Occasionally
SC02_22	Set2: I let other people get their own wa	4 Frequently
SC02_22	Set2: I let other people get their own wa	5 Most of the time
SC02_22	Set2: I let other people get their own wa	6 Always
SC02_22	Set2: I let other people get their own wa	-9 Not answered
SC02_23	Set2: If someone is not with me, he or s	1 Never or almost never
SC02_23	Set2: If someone is not with me, he or s	2 Rarely
SC02_23	Set2: If someone is not with me, he or s	3 Occasionally
SC02_23	Set2: If someone is not with me, he or s	4 Frequently
SC02_23	Set2: If someone is not with me, he or s	5 Most of the time

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SC02_23	Set2: If someone is not with me, he or s	6 Always
SC02_23	Set2: If someone is not with me, he or s	-9 Not answered
SC02_24	Set2: In order to be bothered less by my	1 Never or almost never
SC02_24	Set2: In order to be bothered less by my	2 Rarely
SC02_24	Set2: In order to be bothered less by my	3 Occasionally
SC02_24	Set2: In order to be bothered less by my	4 Frequently
SC02_24	Set2: In order to be bothered less by my	5 Most of the time
SC02_24	Set2: In order to be bothered less by my	6 Always
SC02_24	Set2: In order to be bothered less by my	-9 Not answered
SC02_25	Set2: I'm a bad person if I get angry at c	1 Never or almost never
SC02_25	Set2: I'm a bad person if I get angry at c	2 Rarely
SC02_25	Set2: I'm a bad person if I get angry at c	3 Occasionally
SC02_25	Set2: I'm a bad person if I get angry at c	4 Frequently
SC02_25	Set2: I'm a bad person if I get angry at c	5 Most of the time
SC02_25	Set2: I'm a bad person if I get angry at c	6 Always
SC02_25	Set2: I'm a bad person if I get angry at c	-9 Not answered
SC02_26	Set2: I don't want to get involved with pe	1 Never or almost never
SC02_26	Set2: I don't want to get involved with pe	2 Rarely
SC02_26	Set2: I don't want to get involved with pe	3 Occasionally
SC02_26	Set2: I don't want to get involved with pe	4 Frequently
SC02_26	Set2: I don't want to get involved with pe	5 Most of the time
SC02_26	Set2: I don't want to get involved with pe	6 Always
SC02_26	Set2: I don't want to get involved with pe	-9 Not answered
SC02_27	Set2: I feel that I have plenty of stability	1 Never or almost never
SC02_27	Set2: I feel that I have plenty of stability	2 Rarely
SC02_27	Set2: I feel that I have plenty of stability	3 Occasionally
SC02_27	Set2: I feel that I have plenty of stability	4 Frequently
SC02_27	Set2: I feel that I have plenty of stability	5 Most of the time
SC02_27	Set2: I feel that I have plenty of stability	6 Always
SC02_27	Set2: I feel that I have plenty of stability	-9 Not answered
SC02_28	Set2: I know when to express my emoti	1 Never or almost never
SC02_28	Set2: I know when to express my emoti	2 Rarely
SC02_28	Set2: I know when to express my emoti	3 Occasionally
SC02_28	Set2: I know when to express my emoti	4 Frequently
SC02_28	Set2: I know when to express my emoti	5 Most of the time
SC02_28	Set2: I know when to express my emoti	6 Always
SC02_28	Set2: I know when to express my emoti	-9 Not answered
SC02_29	Set2: I'm angry with someone for leavin	1 Never or almost never
SC02_29	Set2: I'm angry with someone for leavin	2 Rarely
SC02_29	Set2: I'm angry with someone for leavin	3 Occasionally
SC02_29	Set2: I'm angry with someone for leavin	4 Frequently
SC02_29	Set2: I'm angry with someone for leavin	5 Most of the time
SC02_29	Set2: I'm angry with someone for leavin	6 Always
SC02_29	Set2: I'm angry with someone for leavin	-9 Not answered
SC03_01	Set3: I don't feel connected to other pec	1 Never or almost never
SC03_01	Set3: I don't feel connected to other pec	2 Rarely
SC03_01	Set3: I don't feel connected to other pec	3 Occasionally
SC03_01	Set3: I don't feel connected to other pec	4 Frequently
SC03_01	Set3: I don't feel connected to other pec	5 Most of the time
SC03_01	Set3: I don't feel connected to other pec	6 Always
SC03_01	Set3: I don't feel connected to other pec	-9 Not answered
SC03_02	Set3: I can't bring myself to do things th	1 Never or almost never

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SC03_02	Set3: I can't bring myself to do things th.	2 Rarely
SC03_02	Set3: I can't bring myself to do things th.	3 Occasionally
SC03_02	Set3: I can't bring myself to do things th.	4 Frequently
SC03_02	Set3: I can't bring myself to do things th.	5 Most of the time
SC03_02	Set3: I can't bring myself to do things th.	6 Always
SC03_02	Set3: I can't bring myself to do things th.	-9 Not answered
SC03_03	Set3: I break rules and regret it later.	1 Never or almost never
SC03_03	Set3: I break rules and regret it later.	2 Rarely
SC03_03	Set3: I break rules and regret it later.	3 Occasionally
SC03_03	Set3: I break rules and regret it later.	4 Frequently
SC03_03	Set3: I break rules and regret it later.	5 Most of the time
SC03_03	Set3: I break rules and regret it later.	6 Always
SC03_03	Set3: I break rules and regret it later.	-9 Not answered
SC03_04	Set3: I feel humiliated.	1 Never or almost never
SC03_04	Set3: I feel humiliated.	2 Rarely
SC03_04	Set3: I feel humiliated.	3 Occasionally
SC03_04	Set3: I feel humiliated.	4 Frequently
SC03_04	Set3: I feel humiliated.	5 Most of the time
SC03_04	Set3: I feel humiliated.	6 Always
SC03_04	Set3: I feel humiliated.	-9 Not answered
SC03_05	Set3: I trust most other people.	1 Never or almost never
SC03_05	Set3: I trust most other people.	2 Rarely
SC03_05	Set3: I trust most other people.	3 Occasionally
SC03_05	Set3: I trust most other people.	4 Frequently
SC03_05	Set3: I trust most other people.	5 Most of the time
SC03_05	Set3: I trust most other people.	6 Always
SC03_05	Set3: I trust most other people.	-9 Not answered
SC03_06	Set3: I act first and think later.	1 Never or almost never
SC03_06	Set3: I act first and think later.	2 Rarely
SC03_06	Set3: I act first and think later.	3 Occasionally
SC03_06	Set3: I act first and think later.	4 Frequently
SC03_06	Set3: I act first and think later.	5 Most of the time
SC03_06	Set3: I act first and think later.	6 Always
SC03_06	Set3: I act first and think later.	-9 Not answered
SC03_07	Set3: I get bored easily and lose interes	1 Never or almost never
SC03_07	Set3: I get bored easily and lose interes	2 Rarely
SC03_07	Set3: I get bored easily and lose interes	3 Occasionally
SC03_07	Set3: I get bored easily and lose interes	4 Frequently
SC03_07	Set3: I get bored easily and lose interes	5 Most of the time
SC03_07	Set3: I get bored easily and lose interes	6 Always
SC03_07	Set3: I get bored easily and lose interes	-9 Not answered
SC03_08	Set3: Even if there are people around m	1 Never or almost never
SC03_08	Set3: Even if there are people around m	2 Rarely
SC03_08	Set3: Even if there are people around m	3 Occasionally
SC03_08	Set3: Even if there are people around m	4 Frequently
SC03_08	Set3: Even if there are people around m	5 Most of the time
SC03_08	Set3: Even if there are people around m	6 Always
SC03_08	Set3: Even if there are people around m	-9 Not answered
SC03_09	Set3: I don't allow myself to do pleasura	1 Never or almost never
SC03_09	Set3: I don't allow myself to do pleasura	2 Rarely
SC03_09	Set3: I don't allow myself to do pleasura	3 Occasionally
SC03_09	Set3: I don't allow myself to do pleasura	4 Frequently

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SC03_09	Set3: I don't allow myself to do pleasura	5 Most of the time
SC03_09	Set3: I don't allow myself to do pleasura	6 Always
SC03_09	Set3: I don't allow myself to do pleasura	-9 Not answered
SC03_10	Set3: I assert what I need without going	1 Never or almost never
SC03_10	Set3: I assert what I need without going	2 Rarely
SC03_10	Set3: I assert what I need without going	3 Occasionally
SC03_10	Set3: I assert what I need without going	4 Frequently
SC03_10	Set3: I assert what I need without going	5 Most of the time
SC03_10	Set3: I assert what I need without going	6 Always
SC03_10	Set3: I assert what I need without going	-9 Not answered
SC03_11	Set3: I feel special and better than most	1 Never or almost never
SC03_11	Set3: I feel special and better than most	2 Rarely
SC03_11	Set3: I feel special and better than most	3 Occasionally
SC03_11	Set3: I feel special and better than most	4 Frequently
SC03_11	Set3: I feel special and better than most	5 Most of the time
SC03_11	Set3: I feel special and better than most	6 Always
SC03_11	Set3: I feel special and better than most	-9 Not answered
SC03_12	Set3: I don't care about anything; nothin	1 Never or almost never
SC03_12	Set3: I don't care about anything; nothin	2 Rarely
SC03_12	Set3: I don't care about anything; nothin	3 Occasionally
SC03_12	Set3: I don't care about anything; nothin	4 Frequently
SC03_12	Set3: I don't care about anything; nothin	5 Most of the time
SC03_12	Set3: I don't care about anything; nothin	6 Always
SC03_12	Set3: I don't care about anything; nothin	-9 Not answered
SC03_13	Set3: It makes me angry when someone	1 Never or almost never
SC03_13	Set3: It makes me angry when someone	2 Rarely
SC03_13	Set3: It makes me angry when someone	3 Occasionally
SC03_13	Set3: It makes me angry when someone	4 Frequently
SC03_13	Set3: It makes me angry when someone	5 Most of the time
SC03_13	Set3: It makes me angry when someone	6 Always
SC03_13	Set3: It makes me angry when someone	-9 Not answered
SC03_14	Set3: If you don't dominate other people	1 Never or almost never
SC03_14	Set3: If you don't dominate other people	2 Rarely
SC03_14	Set3: If you don't dominate other people	3 Occasionally
SC03_14	Set3: If you don't dominate other people	4 Frequently
SC03_14	Set3: If you don't dominate other people	5 Most of the time
SC03_14	Set3: If you don't dominate other people	6 Always
SC03_14	Set3: If you don't dominate other people	-9 Not answered
SC03_15	Set3: I say what I feel, or do things impu	1 Never or almost never
SC03_15	Set3: I say what I feel, or do things impu	2 Rarely
SC03_15	Set3: I say what I feel, or do things impu	3 Occasionally
SC03_15	Set3: I say what I feel, or do things impu	4 Frequently
SC03_15	Set3: I say what I feel, or do things impu	5 Most of the time
SC03_15	Set3: I say what I feel, or do things impu	6 Always
SC03_15	Set3: I say what I feel, or do things impu	-9 Not answered
SC03_16	Set3: I feel like telling people off for the	1 Never or almost never
SC03_16	Set3: I feel like telling people off for the	2 Rarely
SC03_16	Set3: I feel like telling people off for the	3 Occasionally
SC03_16	Set3: I feel like telling people off for the	4 Frequently
SC03_16	Set3: I feel like telling people off for the	5 Most of the time
SC03_16	Set3: I feel like telling people off for the	6 Always
SC03_16	Set3: I feel like telling people off for the	-9 Not answered

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SC03_17	Set3: I'm capable of taking care of myself.	1 Never or almost never
SC03_17	Set3: I'm capable of taking care of myself.	2 Rarely
SC03_17	Set3: I'm capable of taking care of myself.	3 Occasionally
SC03_17	Set3: I'm capable of taking care of myself.	4 Frequently
SC03_17	Set3: I'm capable of taking care of myself.	5 Most of the time
SC03_17	Set3: I'm capable of taking care of myself.	6 Always
SC03_17	Set3: I'm capable of taking care of myself.	-9 Not answered
SC03_18	Set3: I'm quite critical of other people.	1 Never or almost never
SC03_18	Set3: I'm quite critical of other people.	2 Rarely
SC03_18	Set3: I'm quite critical of other people.	3 Occasionally
SC03_18	Set3: I'm quite critical of other people.	4 Frequently
SC03_18	Set3: I'm quite critical of other people.	5 Most of the time
SC03_18	Set3: I'm quite critical of other people.	6 Always
SC03_18	Set3: I'm quite critical of other people.	-9 Not answered
SC03_19	Set3: I'm under constant pressure to accomplish things.	1 Never or almost never
SC03_19	Set3: I'm under constant pressure to accomplish things.	2 Rarely
SC03_19	Set3: I'm under constant pressure to accomplish things.	3 Occasionally
SC03_19	Set3: I'm under constant pressure to accomplish things.	4 Frequently
SC03_19	Set3: I'm under constant pressure to accomplish things.	5 Most of the time
SC03_19	Set3: I'm under constant pressure to accomplish things.	6 Always
SC03_19	Set3: I'm under constant pressure to accomplish things.	-9 Not answered
SC03_20	Set3: I'm trying not to make mistakes; often I make them.	1 Never or almost never
SC03_20	Set3: I'm trying not to make mistakes; often I make them.	2 Rarely
SC03_20	Set3: I'm trying not to make mistakes; often I make them.	3 Occasionally
SC03_20	Set3: I'm trying not to make mistakes; often I make them.	4 Frequently
SC03_20	Set3: I'm trying not to make mistakes; often I make them.	5 Most of the time
SC03_20	Set3: I'm trying not to make mistakes; often I make them.	6 Always
SC03_20	Set3: I'm trying not to make mistakes; often I make them.	-9 Not answered
SC03_21	Set3: I deserve to be punished.	1 Never or almost never
SC03_21	Set3: I deserve to be punished.	2 Rarely
SC03_21	Set3: I deserve to be punished.	3 Occasionally
SC03_21	Set3: I deserve to be punished.	4 Frequently
SC03_21	Set3: I deserve to be punished.	5 Most of the time
SC03_21	Set3: I deserve to be punished.	6 Always
SC03_21	Set3: I deserve to be punished.	-9 Not answered
SC03_22	Set3: I can learn, grow, and change.	1 Never or almost never
SC03_22	Set3: I can learn, grow, and change.	2 Rarely
SC03_22	Set3: I can learn, grow, and change.	3 Occasionally
SC03_22	Set3: I can learn, grow, and change.	4 Frequently
SC03_22	Set3: I can learn, grow, and change.	5 Most of the time
SC03_22	Set3: I can learn, grow, and change.	6 Always
SC03_22	Set3: I can learn, grow, and change.	-9 Not answered
SC03_23	Set3: I want to distract myself from upsetting thoughts.	1 Never or almost never
SC03_23	Set3: I want to distract myself from upsetting thoughts.	2 Rarely
SC03_23	Set3: I want to distract myself from upsetting thoughts.	3 Occasionally
SC03_23	Set3: I want to distract myself from upsetting thoughts.	4 Frequently
SC03_23	Set3: I want to distract myself from upsetting thoughts.	5 Most of the time
SC03_23	Set3: I want to distract myself from upsetting thoughts.	6 Always
SC03_23	Set3: I want to distract myself from upsetting thoughts.	-9 Not answered
SC03_24	Set3: I'm angry at myself.	1 Never or almost never
SC03_24	Set3: I'm angry at myself.	2 Rarely
SC03_24	Set3: I'm angry at myself.	3 Occasionally

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SC03_24	Set3: I'm angry at myself.	4 Frequently
SC03_24	Set3: I'm angry at myself.	5 Most of the time
SC03_24	Set3: I'm angry at myself.	6 Always
SC03_24	Set3: I'm angry at myself.	-9 Not answered
SC03_25	Set3: I feel flat.	1 Never or almost never
SC03_25	Set3: I feel flat.	2 Rarely
SC03_25	Set3: I feel flat.	3 Occasionally
SC03_25	Set3: I feel flat.	4 Frequently
SC03_25	Set3: I feel flat.	5 Most of the time
SC03_25	Set3: I feel flat.	6 Always
SC03_25	Set3: I feel flat.	-9 Not answered
SC03_26	Set3: I have to be the best in whatever I	1 Never or almost never
SC03_26	Set3: I have to be the best in whatever I	2 Rarely
SC03_26	Set3: I have to be the best in whatever I	3 Occasionally
SC03_26	Set3: I have to be the best in whatever I	4 Frequently
SC03_26	Set3: I have to be the best in whatever I	5 Most of the time
SC03_26	Set3: I have to be the best in whatever I	6 Always
SC03_26	Set3: I have to be the best in whatever I	-9 Not answered
SC03_27	Set3: I sacrifice pleasure, health, or hap	1 Never or almost never
SC03_27	Set3: I sacrifice pleasure, health, or hap	2 Rarely
SC03_27	Set3: I sacrifice pleasure, health, or hap	3 Occasionally
SC03_27	Set3: I sacrifice pleasure, health, or hap	4 Frequently
SC03_27	Set3: I sacrifice pleasure, health, or hap	5 Most of the time
SC03_27	Set3: I sacrifice pleasure, health, or hap	6 Always
SC03_27	Set3: I sacrifice pleasure, health, or hap	-9 Not answered
SC03_28	Set3: I'm demanding of other people.	1 Never or almost never
SC03_28	Set3: I'm demanding of other people.	2 Rarely
SC03_28	Set3: I'm demanding of other people.	3 Occasionally
SC03_28	Set3: I'm demanding of other people.	4 Frequently
SC03_28	Set3: I'm demanding of other people.	5 Most of the time
SC03_28	Set3: I'm demanding of other people.	6 Always
SC03_28	Set3: I'm demanding of other people.	-9 Not answered
SC03_29	Set3: If I get angry, I can get so out of c	1 Never or almost never
SC03_29	Set3: If I get angry, I can get so out of c	2 Rarely
SC03_29	Set3: If I get angry, I can get so out of c	3 Occasionally
SC03_29	Set3: If I get angry, I can get so out of c	4 Frequently
SC03_29	Set3: If I get angry, I can get so out of c	5 Most of the time
SC03_29	Set3: If I get angry, I can get so out of c	6 Always
SC03_29	Set3: If I get angry, I can get so out of c	-9 Not answered
SC04_10	Set4: I am invulnerable.	1 Never or almost never
SC04_10	Set4: I am invulnerable.	2 Rarely
SC04_10	Set4: I am invulnerable.	3 Occasionally
SC04_10	Set4: I am invulnerable.	4 Frequently
SC04_10	Set4: I am invulnerable.	5 Most of the time
SC04_10	Set4: I am invulnerable.	6 Always
SC04_10	Set4: I am invulnerable.	-9 Not answered
SC04_11	Set4: I'm a bad person.	1 Never or almost never
SC04_11	Set4: I'm a bad person.	2 Rarely
SC04_11	Set4: I'm a bad person.	3 Occasionally
SC04_11	Set4: I'm a bad person.	4 Frequently
SC04_11	Set4: I'm a bad person.	5 Most of the time
SC04_11	Set4: I'm a bad person.	6 Always

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SC04_11	Set4: I'm a bad person.	-9 Not answered
SC04_12	Set4: I feel safe.	1 Never or almost never
SC04_12	Set4: I feel safe.	2 Rarely
SC04_12	Set4: I feel safe.	3 Occasionally
SC04_12	Set4: I feel safe.	4 Frequently
SC04_12	Set4: I feel safe.	5 Most of the time
SC04_12	Set4: I feel safe.	6 Always
SC04_12	Set4: I feel safe.	-9 Not answered
SC04_13	Set4: I feel listened to, understood, and	1 Never or almost never
SC04_13	Set4: I feel listened to, understood, and	2 Rarely
SC04_13	Set4: I feel listened to, understood, and	3 Occasionally
SC04_13	Set4: I feel listened to, understood, and	4 Frequently
SC04_13	Set4: I feel listened to, understood, and	5 Most of the time
SC04_13	Set4: I feel listened to, understood, and	6 Always
SC04_13	Set4: I feel listened to, understood, and	-9 Not answered
SC04_14	Set4: It is impossible for me to control r	1 Never or almost never
SC04_14	Set4: It is impossible for me to control r	2 Rarely
SC04_14	Set4: It is impossible for me to control r	3 Occasionally
SC04_14	Set4: It is impossible for me to control r	4 Frequently
SC04_14	Set4: It is impossible for me to control r	5 Most of the time
SC04_14	Set4: It is impossible for me to control r	6 Always
SC04_14	Set4: It is impossible for me to control r	-9 Not answered
SC04_15	Set4: I destroy things when I'm angry.	1 Never or almost never
SC04_15	Set4: I destroy things when I'm angry.	2 Rarely
SC04_15	Set4: I destroy things when I'm angry.	3 Occasionally
SC04_15	Set4: I destroy things when I'm angry.	4 Frequently
SC04_15	Set4: I destroy things when I'm angry.	5 Most of the time
SC04_15	Set4: I destroy things when I'm angry.	6 Always
SC04_15	Set4: I destroy things when I'm angry.	-9 Not answered
SC04_16	Set4: By dominating other people, nothi	1 Never or almost never
SC04_16	Set4: By dominating other people, nothi	2 Rarely
SC04_16	Set4: By dominating other people, nothi	3 Occasionally
SC04_16	Set4: By dominating other people, nothi	4 Frequently
SC04_16	Set4: By dominating other people, nothi	5 Most of the time
SC04_16	Set4: By dominating other people, nothi	6 Always
SC04_16	Set4: By dominating other people, nothi	-9 Not answered
SC04_17	Set4: I act in a passive way, even when	1 Never or almost never
SC04_17	Set4: I act in a passive way, even when	2 Rarely
SC04_17	Set4: I act in a passive way, even when	3 Occasionally
SC04_17	Set4: I act in a passive way, even when	4 Frequently
SC04_17	Set4: I act in a passive way, even when	5 Most of the time
SC04_17	Set4: I act in a passive way, even when	6 Always
SC04_17	Set4: I act in a passive way, even when	-9 Not answered
SC04_18	Set4: My anger gets out of control.	1 Never or almost never
SC04_18	Set4: My anger gets out of control.	2 Rarely
SC04_18	Set4: My anger gets out of control.	3 Occasionally
SC04_18	Set4: My anger gets out of control.	4 Frequently
SC04_18	Set4: My anger gets out of control.	5 Most of the time
SC04_18	Set4: My anger gets out of control.	6 Always
SC04_18	Set4: My anger gets out of control.	-9 Not answered
SC04_19	Set4: I mock or bully other people.	1 Never or almost never
SC04_19	Set4: I mock or bully other people.	2 Rarely

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SC04_19	Set4: I mock or bully other people.	3 Occasionally
SC04_19	Set4: I mock or bully other people.	4 Frequently
SC04_19	Set4: I mock or bully other people.	5 Most of the time
SC04_19	Set4: I mock or bully other people.	6 Always
SC04_19	Set4: I mock or bully other people.	-9 Not answered
SC04_20	Set4: I feel like lashing out or hurting so	1 Never or almost never
SC04_20	Set4: I feel like lashing out or hurting so	2 Rarely
SC04_20	Set4: I feel like lashing out or hurting so	3 Occasionally
SC04_20	Set4: I feel like lashing out or hurting so	4 Frequently
SC04_20	Set4: I feel like lashing out or hurting so	5 Most of the time
SC04_20	Set4: I feel like lashing out or hurting so	6 Always
SC04_20	Set4: I feel like lashing out or hurting so	-9 Not answered
SC04_21	Set4: I know that there is a "right" and a	1 Never or almost never
SC04_21	Set4: I know that there is a "right" and a	2 Rarely
SC04_21	Set4: I know that there is a "right" and a	3 Occasionally
SC04_21	Set4: I know that there is a "right" and a	4 Frequently
SC04_21	Set4: I know that there is a "right" and a	5 Most of the time
SC04_21	Set4: I know that there is a "right" and a	6 Always
SC04_21	Set4: I know that there is a "right" and a	-9 Not answered
SC04_22	Set4: I often feel alone in the world.	1 Never or almost never
SC04_22	Set4: I often feel alone in the world.	2 Rarely
SC04_22	Set4: I often feel alone in the world.	3 Occasionally
SC04_22	Set4: I often feel alone in the world.	4 Frequently
SC04_22	Set4: I often feel alone in the world.	5 Most of the time
SC04_22	Set4: I often feel alone in the world.	6 Always
SC04_22	Set4: I often feel alone in the world.	-9 Not answered
SC04_23	Set4: I feel weak and helpless.	1 Never or almost never
SC04_23	Set4: I feel weak and helpless.	2 Rarely
SC04_23	Set4: I feel weak and helpless.	3 Occasionally
SC04_23	Set4: I feel weak and helpless.	4 Frequently
SC04_23	Set4: I feel weak and helpless.	5 Most of the time
SC04_23	Set4: I feel weak and helpless.	6 Always
SC04_23	Set4: I feel weak and helpless.	-9 Not answered
SC04_24	Set4: I'm lazy.	1 Never or almost never
SC04_24	Set4: I'm lazy.	2 Rarely
SC04_24	Set4: I'm lazy.	3 Occasionally
SC04_24	Set4: I'm lazy.	4 Frequently
SC04_24	Set4: I'm lazy.	5 Most of the time
SC04_24	Set4: I'm lazy.	6 Always
SC04_24	Set4: I'm lazy.	-9 Not answered
SC04_25	Set4: I can put up with anything from pe	1 Never or almost never
SC04_25	Set4: I can put up with anything from pe	2 Rarely
SC04_25	Set4: I can put up with anything from pe	3 Occasionally
SC04_25	Set4: I can put up with anything from pe	4 Frequently
SC04_25	Set4: I can put up with anything from pe	5 Most of the time
SC04_25	Set4: I can put up with anything from pe	6 Always
SC04_25	Set4: I can put up with anything from pe	-9 Not answered
SC04_26	Set4: I've been cheated or treated unfai	1 Never or almost never
SC04_26	Set4: I've been cheated or treated unfai	2 Rarely
SC04_26	Set4: I've been cheated or treated unfai	3 Occasionally
SC04_26	Set4: I've been cheated or treated unfai	4 Frequently
SC04_26	Set4: I've been cheated or treated unfai	5 Most of the time

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SC04_26	Set4: I've been cheated or treated unfai	6 Always
SC04_26	Set4: I've been cheated or treated unfai	-9 Not answered
SC04_27	Set4: I feel left out or excluded.	1 Never or almost never
SC04_27	Set4: I feel left out or excluded.	2 Rarely
SC04_27	Set4: I feel left out or excluded.	3 Occasionally
SC04_27	Set4: I feel left out or excluded.	4 Frequently
SC04_27	Set4: I feel left out or excluded.	5 Most of the time
SC04_27	Set4: I feel left out or excluded.	6 Always
SC04_27	Set4: I feel left out or excluded.	-9 Not answered
SC04_28	Set4: I belittle others	1 Never or almost never
SC04_28	Set4: I belittle others	2 Rarely
SC04_28	Set4: I belittle others	3 Occasionally
SC04_28	Set4: I belittle others	4 Frequently
SC04_28	Set4: I belittle others	5 Most of the time
SC04_28	Set4: I belittle others	6 Always
SC04_28	Set4: I belittle others	-9 Not answered
SC04_29	Set4: I feel optimistic.	1 Never or almost never
SC04_29	Set4: I feel optimistic.	2 Rarely
SC04_29	Set4: I feel optimistic.	3 Occasionally
SC04_29	Set4: I feel optimistic.	4 Frequently
SC04_29	Set4: I feel optimistic.	5 Most of the time
SC04_29	Set4: I feel optimistic.	6 Always
SC04_29	Set4: I feel optimistic.	-9 Not answered
SC04_30	Set4: I feel I shouldn't have to follow the	1 Never or almost never
SC04_30	Set4: I feel I shouldn't have to follow the	2 Rarely
SC04_30	Set4: I feel I shouldn't have to follow the	3 Occasionally
SC04_30	Set4: I feel I shouldn't have to follow the	4 Frequently
SC04_30	Set4: I feel I shouldn't have to follow the	5 Most of the time
SC04_30	Set4: I feel I shouldn't have to follow the	6 Always
SC04_30	Set4: I feel I shouldn't have to follow the	-9 Not answered
SC04_31	Set4: I'm pushing myself to be more res	1 Never or almost never
SC04_31	Set4: I'm pushing myself to be more res	2 Rarely
SC04_31	Set4: I'm pushing myself to be more res	3 Occasionally
SC04_31	Set4: I'm pushing myself to be more res	4 Frequently
SC04_31	Set4: I'm pushing myself to be more res	5 Most of the time
SC04_31	Set4: I'm pushing myself to be more res	6 Always
SC04_31	Set4: I'm pushing myself to be more res	-9 Not answered
SC04_32	Set4: I can stand up for myself when I fe	1 Never or almost never
SC04_32	Set4: I can stand up for myself when I fe	2 Rarely
SC04_32	Set4: I can stand up for myself when I fe	3 Occasionally
SC04_32	Set4: I can stand up for myself when I fe	4 Frequently
SC04_32	Set4: I can stand up for myself when I fe	5 Most of the time
SC04_32	Set4: I can stand up for myself when I fe	6 Always
SC04_32	Set4: I can stand up for myself when I fe	-9 Not answered
SC04_33	Set4: I don't deserve sympathy when so	1 Never or almost never
SC04_33	Set4: I don't deserve sympathy when so	2 Rarely
SC04_33	Set4: I don't deserve sympathy when so	3 Occasionally
SC04_33	Set4: I don't deserve sympathy when so	4 Frequently
SC04_33	Set4: I don't deserve sympathy when so	5 Most of the time
SC04_33	Set4: I don't deserve sympathy when so	6 Always
SC04_33	Set4: I don't deserve sympathy when so	-9 Not answered
SC04_34	Set4: I feel that nobody loves me.	1 Never or almost never

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SC04_34	Set4: I feel that nobody loves me.	2 Rarely
SC04_34	Set4: I feel that nobody loves me.	3 Occasionally
SC04_34	Set4: I feel that nobody loves me.	4 Frequently
SC04_34	Set4: I feel that nobody loves me.	5 Most of the time
SC04_34	Set4: I feel that nobody loves me.	6 Always
SC04_34	Set4: I feel that nobody loves me.	-9 Not answered
SC04_35	Set4: I feel that I'm basically a good per	1 Never or almost never
SC04_35	Set4: I feel that I'm basically a good per	2 Rarely
SC04_35	Set4: I feel that I'm basically a good per	3 Occasionally
SC04_35	Set4: I feel that I'm basically a good per	4 Frequently
SC04_35	Set4: I feel that I'm basically a good per	5 Most of the time
SC04_35	Set4: I feel that I'm basically a good per	6 Always
SC04_35	Set4: I feel that I'm basically a good per	-9 Not answered
SC04_36	Set4: When necessary, I complete borir	1 Never or almost never
SC04_36	Set4: When necessary, I complete borir	2 Rarely
SC04_36	Set4: When necessary, I complete borir	3 Occasionally
SC04_36	Set4: When necessary, I complete borir	4 Frequently
SC04_36	Set4: When necessary, I complete borir	5 Most of the time
SC04_36	Set4: When necessary, I complete borir	6 Always
SC04_36	Set4: When necessary, I complete borir	-9 Not answered
SC04_37	Set4: I feel spontaneous and playful.	1 Never or almost never
SC04_37	Set4: I feel spontaneous and playful.	2 Rarely
SC04_37	Set4: I feel spontaneous and playful.	3 Occasionally
SC04_37	Set4: I feel spontaneous and playful.	4 Frequently
SC04_37	Set4: I feel spontaneous and playful.	5 Most of the time
SC04_37	Set4: I feel spontaneous and playful.	6 Always
SC04_37	Set4: I feel spontaneous and playful.	-9 Not answered
SC04_38	Set4: I can become so angry that I feel c	1 Never or almost never
SC04_38	Set4: I can become so angry that I feel c	2 Rarely
SC04_38	Set4: I can become so angry that I feel c	3 Occasionally
SC04_38	Set4: I can become so angry that I feel c	4 Frequently
SC04_38	Set4: I can become so angry that I feel c	5 Most of the time
SC04_38	Set4: I can become so angry that I feel c	6 Always
SC04_38	Set4: I can become so angry that I feel c	-9 Not answered
SC04_39	Set4: I have a good sense of who I am a	1 Never or almost never
SC04_39	Set4: I have a good sense of who I am a	2 Rarely
SC04_39	Set4: I have a good sense of who I am a	3 Occasionally
SC04_39	Set4: I have a good sense of who I am a	4 Frequently
SC04_39	Set4: I have a good sense of who I am a	5 Most of the time
SC04_39	Set4: I have a good sense of who I am a	6 Always
SC04_39	Set4: I have a good sense of who I am a	-9 Not answered
SD02	Nationality	-2 other text response
SD02	Nationality	-9 Not answered
SD02s	Nationality (free text)	
SD04	Age	1 14
SD04	Age	2 15
SD04	Age	3 16
SD04	Age	4 17
SD04	Age	5 18
SD04	Age	6 19
SD04	Age	7 20
SD04	Age	8 21

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SD04	Age	9 22
SD04	Age	10 23
SD04	Age	11 24
SD04	Age	12 25
SD04	Age	13 26
SD04	Age	14 27
SD04	Age	15 28
SD04	Age	16 29
SD04	Age	17 30
SD04	Age	18 31
SD04	Age	19 32
SD04	Age	20 33
SD04	Age	21 34
SD04	Age	22 35
SD04	Age	23 36
SD04	Age	24 37
SD04	Age	25 38
SD04	Age	26 39
SD04	Age	27 40
SD04	Age	28 41
SD04	Age	29 42
SD04	Age	30 43
SD04	Age	31 44
SD04	Age	32 45
SD04	Age	33 46
SD04	Age	34 47
SD04	Age	35 48
SD04	Age	36 49
SD04	Age	37 50
SD04	Age	38 51
SD04	Age	39 52
SD04	Age	40 53
SD04	Age	41 54
SD04	Age	42 55
SD04	Age	43 56
SD04	Age	44 57
SD04	Age	45 58
SD04	Age	46 59
SD04	Age	47 60
SD04	Age	48 61
SD04	Age	49 62
SD04	Age	50 63
SD04	Age	-9 Not answered
SD05	Consent	1 I agree
SD05	Consent	2 I don't agree
SD05	Consent	-9 Not answered
SD06_01	English language: I do not understand E	1 I do not understand English
SD06_01	English language: I do not understand E	101 I am a native speaker of English
SD06_01	English language: I do not understand E	-9 Not answered
SD07	Gender	1 female
SD07	Gender	2 male
SD07	Gender	3 other

MusicSchemata

SD07	Gender	4 prefer not to say
SD07	Gender	-9 Not answered
TX07_01	Feedback: [01]	
TIME001	Time spent on page 1	
TIME002	Time spent on page 2	
TIME003	Time spent on page 3	
TIME004	Time spent on page 4	
TIME005	Time spent on page 5	
TIME006	Time spent on page 6	
TIME007	Time spent on page 7	
TIME008	Time spent on page 8	
TIME009	Time spent on page 9	
TIME010	Time spent on page 10	
TIME_SUM	Time spent overall (except outliers)	
MAILSENT	Time when the invitation mailing was sent (personally identifiable recipients, only)	
LASTDATA	Time when the data was most recently updated	
FINISHED	Has the interview been finished (reache	0 Canceled
FINISHED	Has the interview been finished (reache	1 Finished
Q_VIEWER	Did the respondent only view the questik	0 Respondent
Q_VIEWER	Did the respondent only view the questik	1 Spectator
LASTPAGE	Last page that the participant has handled in the questionnaire	
MAXPAGE	Hindmost page handled by the participant	
MISSING	Missing answers in percent	
MISSREL	Missing answers (weighted by relevance)	
TIME_RSI	Completion Speed (relative)	

MusicSchemata

METRIC	NUM

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MusicSchemata

ORDINAL	MC
TEXT	TXT
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MusicSchemata

NOMINAL	MC
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TEXT	TXT
METRIC	TXT
TIME	TXT
TIME	TXT
BOOL	TXT
METRIC	TXT

To access the detailed evaluation data, please contact the corresponding author or Prof. Dr. med. Horst Hildebrandt via email horst.hildebrandt@zhdk.ch

Thank you!